

Analysis protocol for the project “Screening for impaired pulmonary function using mechanical peak flow meters: Performance of different interpretation strategies”

1 Document version

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2 Project partners

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3 Background

While spirometry is the gold standard for diagnosis of pulmonary function impairment, it is often not available in low-income settings. Measurement of peak expiratory flow (PEF) is sometimes recommended as an alternative to spirometry when the latter is not available, but there has been no consensus on how to define the PEF cutoffs that determine whether one should consider a persons’ lung function impaired. Some authors have used cutoffs based on absolute value of PEF, others PEF in percent predicted, $PEF \times \text{height}^{-2}$, PEF Z-score or gender-specific cutoffs based on absolute value of PEF. In a recent study, MRHH and JMS showed that PEF in percent predicted and PEF Z-score outperformed the other strategies, defined by having a higher Area Under the Curve (AUC) for the detection of low Z-score for Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV_1 Z-score).¹ However, the study by MRHH and JMS was limited by relying on PEF measurements from quality-controlled spirometry maneuvers instead of mechanical peak flow meters.

4 Purpose

The purpose of the proposed study is replicate the findings of MRHH and JMS based on a study population where PEF has been measured by mechanical peak flow meters, to better reflect the real-world situation in which PEF may be used as a surrogate for spirometry. Specifically, we will

- 1) Compare the AUC between the above-mentioned PEF interpretation strategies to determine the “best” strategy, defined as the strategy with the highest AUC. The outcome to be predicted is impaired pulmonary function, defined by low FEV₁ Z-score.
- 2) Provide tables of sensitivity and specificity at a number of cutoffs for each PEF interpretation strategy so that clinicians using PEF to screen for impaired pulmonary function can decide on an appropriate cutoff to use.

5 Materials and methods

5.1 Source of data

The project will be based on an analysis of data collected as part of the CECYP study (“Cribado de EPOC por cuestionario y pico de flujo”), which was conducted in Spain and has been described in detail elsewhere.² The CECYP project included spirometry and PEF measurements from mechanical peak flow meters (Mini-Wright).

5.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

5.2.1 Inclusion criteria

Participants were selected among patients (men and women) consulting their general practitioner for any reason, and who...

- 1) Were aged 35-85 (persons above 85 years could be included in the CECYP study, but are not eligible for the present study because the equations for calculating predicted values of PEF in Spanish adults are not validated in persons above 85 years)
- 2) Had no previous diagnosis of COPD.
- 3) Attended their general practitioner for any reason (apart from an acute respiratory illness).
- 4) Signed an informed consent form.

5.2.2 Exclusion criteria

Subjects who...

- 1) Attended their general practitioner for an acute respiratory illness.
- 2) Had previous diagnoses of pulmonary diseases that may cause obstruction (asthma, bronchiectasis).
- 3) Had allergy to bronchodilator medication (although the present analysis will be limited to pre-bronchodilator spirometry).

- 4) Had any contraindication for spirometry: Failure to understand or comply with instructions for examinations, failure to conduct the examinations, illnesses causing thoracic pain (pneumothorax, angina pectoris, etc.), recent hemoptysis, thoracic or cerebral aneurism, recent myocardial infarction, recent retinal detachment or cataract surgery, tracheostomy, absence of dental prostheses.
- 5) Had significant comorbidity that could interfere with spirometry results (severe chronic renal insufficiency, severe hepatic insufficiency, active cancer, or immunodeficiency).
- 6) Already participated in any clinical studies.
- 7) Were physically or mentally incapable of understanding the information provided to them, and/or to answer the questions asked by the doctor.

5.2.3 Differences from the original CECYP study

The original CECYP study had a two-stage design. In a first (large) stage participants only underwent spirometry if the either had a COPD-PS score ≥ 4 , or if they had $PEF \times \text{height}^{-2} \leq 2.2 \text{ L/s/m}^2$. In a second (smaller) stage with other participants, all participants underwent spirometry, and were classified as having obstruction or not based on FEV_1/FVC (fixed cutoff of 0.7).

The main analysis in the present study will include participants from both stages of CECYP, but only those with COPD-PS score ≥ 4 (we will not select participants based on $PEF \times \text{height}^{-2} \leq 2.2 \text{ L/s/m}^2$). We will focus on low FEV_1 Z-score as outcome, without regarding the FEV_1/FVC ratio. In sensitivity analyses, we will include participants only from the second stage of CECYP, and without regards for COPD-PS score or $PEF \times \text{height}^{-2}$.

5.3 Principle of analyses

For each of the measures PEF, PEF in percent predicted, PEF z-score, $PEF \times \text{height}^{-2}$, we will calculate the AUC (area under the receiver operating curve) for the detection of impaired lung function (defined as FEV_1 Z-score < -1.645 , < -2 , < -2.5 , < -3 and < -4), and the difference in AUC between the different measures. This will be done both for the entire study population, and stratified by gender. Secondary and sensitivity analyses may use other outcomes; we will only analyze outcome with at least 20 cases.

AUC, sensitivity and specificity will be calculated using standard formulae. Confidence intervals will be derived using standard formulae where available – when these are not available, or the assumptions underlying the formulae are not fulfilled, we will instead derive confidence intervals by bootstrapping (bias-corrected bootstrap intervals with 1000 samples). Table 3 provides an overview of the planned analyses, including secondary and sensitivity analyses.

5.4 Details of analyses

5.4.1 Removal of invalid data

CECYP data were collected by a large number of general practitioners (GPs), not all of whom may have adhered to protocol (conducting quality-controlled spirometry, measuring PEF with mechanical peak flow meters instead of relying on PEF from spirometry). We will remove such measurements by the following criteria:

Table 1

Criterion for exclusion of observation	Reason
PEF (in L/min) is > 0 and < 60	The Mini-Wright peak flow meter has a scale from 60 to 880 L/min, in steps of 10-20 L/min. PEF measurements with the indicated values are likely to be caused either by data entry errors, or by measuring PEF with spirometers.
PEF (in L/min) is > 880	
PEF (in L/min) is non-integer	
PEF (in L/min) is not a multiple of 5	
FEV ₁ implausibly low (< 400 mL for women or < 500 ml for men)	FEV ₁ values below this range are deemed incompatible with life, ³ and likely represent low-quality spirometric maneuvers, rather than reflect pulmonary function of the tested individual.
≥50% of spirometries from the same GP have implausibly low values of FEV ₁	If the majority of spirometries from a GP have implausibly low FEV ₁ , we suspect that the remaining spirometries from the same GP may also be erroneous.

5.4.2 Rounding of PEF metrics

Before ROC curves are constructed, the various PEF metrics will be rounded off. Absolute value of PEF is already reported as a multiple of 5 L/min. PEF in percent predicted will be rounded off to the nearest multiple of 0.5. PEF Z-score will be rounded off to the nearest multiple of 0.1. PEF×height⁻² will be rounded off to the nearest multiple of 1 L/min/m².

5.4.3 Predicted values

Predicted values and Z-scores for FEV₁, FVC and FEV₁/FVC will be calculated using the GLI 2012 equations.⁴ In accordance with recommendations⁵ from the Spanish Society for Pneumology and Thoracic Surgery, predicted values and Z-scores for PEF will be calculated using separate formulas for persons aged 20-65⁶ and 65-80.⁷

5.4.4 Descriptive statistics

For each analysis, we will create a table of descriptive statistics, the structure of which is indicated in

Table 2.

Table 2

Parameter		Result
Total n		n
Gender	Male	n (%)
	Female	n (%)
Age		Mean (SD)
Height		Mean (SD)
Smoking status	Never	n (%)
	Former	n (%)
	Active	n (%)
	Missing	n (%)
COPD-PS score		Mean (SD)
FEV ₁		Mean (SD)
FEV ₁ % predicted		Mean (SD)
FEV ₁ Z-score		Mean (SD)
FVC		Mean (SD)
		n missing
FVC % predicted		Mean (SD)
		n missing
FVC Z-score		Mean (SD)
		n missing
FEV ₁ /FVC		Mean (SD)
		n missing
FEV ₁ /FVC % predicted		Mean (SD)
		n missing
FEV ₁ /FVC Z-score		Mean (SD)
		n missing
PEF		Mean (SD)
PEF % predicted		Mean (SD)
PEF Z-score		Mean (SD)
PEF×height ²		Mean (SD)

There is no “n missing” for age, height, COPD-PS score, FEV₁, and PEF, since missing values in these variables will lead to exclusion from the study.

5.4.5 Flowchart of inclusion and exclusion

For each analysis, we will create a STROBE flowchart⁸ describing in detail how the number of participants in this analysis was arrived at.

5.5 Publication

5.5.1 Pre-publication of project protocol

Before analyses commence, the project protocol will be deposited online at Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) and put under embargo to be released to the public no later than January 1, 2026.

5.5.2 Final paper

The results of the analysis will be published in an international, peer-reviewed scientific journal under a Gold Open Access license. We will choose a journal that has an agreement with Aarhus University to allow waiving the open access fee.⁹

The final paper will include an appendix with tables of sensitivity and specificity (including 95% CI) at a number of cutoffs for each PEF interpretation strategy.

6 Ethics

Participants in the original CECYP study gave informed consent before inclusion, and the CECYP project was approved by the Ethics Committee for Clinical Research of the Balearic Islands, Palma de Mallorca, Spain (IB 2142/13 EPA, 25 July 2013).

Under Danish legislation, no ethical review is needed for new studies that are solely based on reanalyses of already collected data.¹⁰ The Danish National Center for Ethics¹¹ has confirmed that the proposed project does not require any permission from an ethical committee in Denmark (personal communication, Anna Bundgaard Fønss, May 31 2023). The processing of personal data in the project has been reported to Danish Data Protection Agency.

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Table 3

Analysis number	Type of analysis	Binary condition to be predicted	Predictors	Gender	Inclusion criterion for FEV ₁	CECYP cohort	Inclusion criterion for COPD-PS	Comment
1	Primary	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF ×height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	The outcome to be predicted is different degrees of FEV ₁ impairment.
2	Primary	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF ×height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for males and females	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	As analysis 1, but separate analysis by gender. This is because some authors have used gender-specific cutoffs when predicting obstruction using absolute values of PEF. This analysis will show how Z-scores and % predicted perform compared to gender-specific cutoffs of absolute PEF or PEF ×height ⁻² . In addition to the ROC plots, the sensitivity and specificity at each cutoff will be compared between genders.
3	Secondary (A)	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN with FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF ×height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	The outcome to be predicted is different degrees of airway obstruction (not just FEV ₁ impairment as in analysis 1).
4	Secondary (B)	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN	PEF PEF ×height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Participants with FEV ₁ z-score < -1.645	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	This analysis is limited to participants with FEV ₁ impairment, and the outcome to be predicted is obstruction. It is expected that the performance of the model will be poor.
5	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ % < 80, 50 or 30	PEF PEF ×height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	As analysis 1, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of FEV ₁ impairment.

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6	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ % < 80, 50 or 30	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for males and females	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	As analysis 2, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of FEV ₁ impairment.
7	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < 0.7 with FEV ₁ % < 80, 50 or 30	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	As analysis 3, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of airway obstruction, and using a fixed cutoff for FEV ₁ /FVC.
8	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < 0.7	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Participants with FEV ₁ % < 80	First (“main”) and second (“validation”) cohort	COPD-PS ≥ 4	As analysis 4, but defining obstruction based on a fixed cutoff for FEV ₁ /FVC, and with impaired FEV ₁ defined as < 80% predicted.
9	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	Second (“validation”) cohort	N/A	As analysis 1, but based on only the second CECYP cohort, and not limiting participants based on COPD-PS score
10	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for males and females	N/A	Second (“validation”) cohort	N/A	As analysis 2, but based on only the second CECYP cohort, and not limiting participants based on COPD-PS score
11	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN with FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	N/A	Second (“validation”) cohort	N/A	As analysis 3, but based on only the second CECYP cohort, and not limiting participants based on COPD-PS score
12	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN	PEF PEF × height ⁻² PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Participants with FEV ₁ z-score < -1.645	Second (“validation”) cohort (“validation”) cohort	N/A	As analysis 4, but based on only the second CECYP cohort, and not limiting participants based on COPD-PS score

N/A = not applicable

7 References

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